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Executive Summary

This document describes the first version of new data products for sustainable fisheries developed in the ARCFISH project. This project is funded by the Research Councils of Norway (Research Council of Norway (RCN)), Portugal (Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT)), Poland (The National Centre for Research and Development, Poland (NCBR)), Denmark (Innovation Fund Denmark (IFD)) and Iceland (The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS)), after successful evaluation of the proposals for the 2023 First Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership Joint Transnational Co-Funded Call.

ARCFISH will develop a pilot Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) supporting sustainable fisheries in the Arctic. The DTO will be based on the existing Blue Insight platform that seamlessly supports the market segments of the ocean observing value chain of the New Blue Economy (Heslop et al., 2022). The New Blue Economy, also known as the Sustainable Blue Economy (SBE), is a concept that promotes sustainable development and conservation of ocean resources for economic, social, and environmental benefits. In the Arctic, sustainable fisheries focusing on achieving long-term sustainability and resilience of ocean ecosystems and communities is the key to uphold good living conditions for its residents. However, the negative impacts of traditional economic activities such as overfishing, marine pollution, habitat destruction, and climate change have threatened the health and sustainability of the ocean, leading to declining fish stocks, loss of biodiversity, and increased coastal vulnerability to natural disasters. New data products and services, co-developed with relevant stakeholders, are needed to provide a better basis for decision-making in fisheries planning and management. For example, for Disko Bay, western Greenland, ecosystem indices based on an improved ecosystem model could include monthly spatial maps of zooplankton biomass and production, benthos biomass, shrimp biomass, and upwelling areas. Data collected around Iceland towards the Barents Sea onboard fishing vessels and in seafood processing could be implemented in the DTO to support relevant stakeholders. For the Arctic in general, potential new services could include advanced eLogbooks and spatio-temporal pattern detection and visualisation. For cost-efficiency these services must leverage novel digital technologies such as DTOs to acquire, process, analyse and visualise heterogeneous data from a wide range of sources.

More information on the project can be found at: <https://www.arcfish.eu/>.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
AIS	Automatic Identification System
BGC	Biogeochemical
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Service
CTD	Conductivity, Temperature, and Depth
DITTO	Digital Twins of the Ocean program of the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
eCUDO	Electronic Center for Sharing Oceanographic Data
ERGOM	Ecological ReGional Ocean Model
ERS	Electronic Reporting System
EMODNET	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EUMETSAT	European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites
FDD	Fisheries-dependent data
EDITO	European Digital Twin Ocean
GEBCO	General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans
GEM	Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring
ICES	International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
ILIAD	Integrated digital solution facilitates access to oceanic data and boosts decision-making
INTAROS	Integrated Arctic observation system
MCS	Monitoring, control and surveillance
NMDC	Norwegian Marine Data Centre
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OSISAF	Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility
RF	Recreational fisheries
SBE	Sustainable Blue Economy
SBEP	Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership
SSF	Small-scale fisheries
VMS	Vessel Monitoring System

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

ARCFISH will develop a pilot Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) Platform delivering new data products and services in support of sustainable Arctic Fisheries. These data products and services will be co-designed with stakeholders in the fisheries sector and used to create products such as ecosystem indices that can be applied in fisheries planning and management. Available data sources and gaps will be analysed to fulfil user needs and ingest relevant data into the Blue Insight DTO Platform. They include (1) oceanographic data from research vessels, autonomous mobile platforms, fixed buoys, and ships of opportunity such as fishing vessels, (2) met-ice-ocean forecasts and reanalysis from models (e.g., from CMEMS and INTAROS), (3) fisheries management data (e.g., fisheries stocks, species) from ICES and national sources, and (4) reference data (e.g., bathymetry, economic zones, AIS data).

Based on stakeholder needs, a use case for sustainable fisheries will be implemented using the ingested data and tools for generating customised products. The use case will address two geographic regions, the west coast of Greenland centred around the rich fishing grounds surrounding Disko Bay, and the region around Iceland, northwards to the Svalbard archipelago and the Barents Sea. Using the compiled data and developed tools, a regional database of climate, environmental, and fisheries data will be created and made available through an open data repository to support sustainable Arctic Fisheries. This important asset will contribute to the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership (SBEP) program by providing new data products that can be utilised in DTO platforms to support decision-making in fisheries management.

The Blue Insight platform developed by Kongsberg Discovery, Norway, will be part of the Digital Twins of the Ocean (DITTO) program of the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development. As part of DITTO and through engagement with other running DTO projects and initiatives such as EDITO, ILIAD, Blue-Cloud2026 and EOSC, ARCFISH development will follow standards for data exchange and implementation of services and tools in the EU DTO. ARCFISH will prepare training material for using the Blue Insight DTO platform and organise capacity building events for stakeholders and other SBE projects. Training will be organised in conjunction with project meetings and SBEP events. Furthermore, the regional database, developed services and tools, training and promotional material will be promoted through the iAOS portal from INTAROS, a public project website linked to relevant DTO sites, through the ARCFISH website, and dedicated social media channels. ARCFISH results will also be promoted through the partners' extensive network of Arctic observing and data management, digital technologies, capacity building in ocean literacy, stakeholder interaction and fisheries.

1.2. Organisation of the document

The structure of this document is as follows. Chapter 2 provides a short introduction on the new data products and regional database that will be ingested into the Blue Insight DTO platform. Chapter 3 presents the first version of the modelling products from Disko Bay, Greenland, model system. Chapters 4 and 5 present environmental time-series data and fishery-dependent data from research projects, operational services, databases, *in-situ* data and monitoring programmes in the regions addressed by the two case studies. Chapter 6 showcase the regional database for the two use cases. The final chapter, Chapter 7, summarizes the work to prepare a first set of new data products for ARCFISH and plans for enhancing the products offered through the Blue Insight DTO platform for the ARCFISH community.

2. Short introduction on the new data products and regional database

Based on stakeholder needs from WP1 (multi-stakeholder co-creation of the Arctic DTO) and data ingested in WP2 (Data ingestion services), partners will develop new data products for sustainable fisheries. The products will be available in the Blue Insight DTO platform operated by Kongsberg Discovery and used to create a public regional database. New data products will be developed either from measurements made by the project partners, from in-situ sources or from models developed by the project partners in this or other projects.

Extending ecosystem models with a richer representation of the complex interactions in the marine food web will facilitate new products tailored for sound management and utilisation of fisheries resources under today's rapidly changing climate conditions. Time-series of water column physical and if/where available, biogeochemical properties from *in situ* platforms, augmented with selected outputs of reanalysis models will be produced to provide comprehensive information on environmental background for fishery data. Fishery-dependent data will be coupled with fishery-independent data and then integrated into the DTO. Fishery-dependent data can include fishing pressure, gear, catch composition, size distribution, condition factor, yield, nematodes etc. Fishery-independent information includes oceanographic-, meteorological-, social, and economic data. Further, a collection of the data integrated for the use cases will be gathered into a regional database.

Integrating new model projections, available observations and powerful analysis tools in a DTO platform will open for novel ways of investigating and visualising trends and patterns in species distribution and abundance. Enhancing scientific analysis tools with new algorithms (e.g., machine learning, big data analytics) integrated in the powerful DTO infrastructure will allow more efficient exploitation of the vast amount of data currently available from a broad range of sources (including real-time). This can in turn foster innovations in predicting future scenarios for better informed decision-making and policymaking for a sustainable Blue Economy in Arctic regions.

3. Ecological indices from modelling

3.1. Disko Bay ecosystem model

About 60,000 people live in Greenland and most of them along the West coast. They are traditionally highly dependent on the marine ecosystem and Greenland's economy is presently strongly related to the productivity of the marine waters. With a changing climate regime, i.e. reduction of ice thickness and increasing temperature, an increase in commercial fisheries is likely. Disko Bay is located on the west coast of Greenland at the southern border of the Arctic Sea ice and is influenced by both sub-Arctic waters from southwestern Greenland and Arctic waters from Baffin Bay. Disko Bay is an important "hot spot" for biodiversity and fisheries, and one of the best studied areas in Greenland. The Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (GEM) program provides data on oceanography, nutrients, phytoplankton, and zooplankton. Fish stocks are monitored by the Greenland Institute of Natural Resources.

Figure 1: FlexSem ecosystem model. Copernicus data is used to force and validate the model, and Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (GEM) program has local data from Disko Bay. The 3D model uses an unstructured grid and is coupled to a biogeochem.

The 3D dynamic model of Disko Bay was developed in the EU INTAROS project using local measurements and Copernicus data for model forcing, calibration, and validation (Figure 1). The model was set up using the FlexSem model system (Larsen et al. 2020). FlexSem is an open-source modular framework for 3D unstructured marine modelling. The system contains modules for hydrostatic and non-hydrostatic hydrodynamics, 3D pelagic and 3D benthic models, sediment transport, and agent-based models. The FlexSem source code and precompiled source code for Windows (GNU General Public License) can be downloaded at <https://marweb.bios.au.dk/Flexsem>. The specific code for the Disko set-up can be downloaded on <https://zenodo.org/> (Larsen, 2025; Maar et al., 2025).

Bathymetry was obtained from the 150x150 m resolved IceBridge BedMachine Greenland, Version 3 (<https://nsidc.org/data/IDBMG4>) and interpolated to the FlexSem computational mesh using linear interpolation. The 96,300 km² large computational mesh for the Disko Bay area was constructed using the mesh generator JigSaw (<https://github.com/dengwirda/jigsaw>) (Figure 2). It consists of 6,349 elements and 34 depth z-layers with a total of 105,678 computational cells. The horizontal resolution varies from 1.8 km in the Disko Bay proper, 4.7 km in Strait of Vaigat and 16 km towards the semi-circular Baffin Bay open boundary. In the deepest layers, the vertical resolution is 50 m, decreasing towards the surface, where the top 5 layers are 3.5, 1.5, 2.0, 2.0 and 2.0 meters thick, respectively. The surface layer thickness is flexible, allowing changes in water level, e.g. due to tidal elevations. The model time step is 300 seconds, and it has been run for the period from 2004 to 2018. The MAR and RCMO regional climate model (RCM) runoff field was used to compute freshwater discharge. The long-term sea ice cover within Disko Bay was extracted from daily sea ice concentration data provided by the EUMETSAT Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility (OSISAF, www.osi-saf.org, Lavergne et al., 2019). More detailed information of the model configuration can be found in Møller et al. (2023).

The biogeochemical model in the FlexSem framework was based on a modification of the ERGOM model that originally was applied to the Baltic Sea and the North Sea (Møller et al. 2023). In the Disko Bay version, 11 state

variables describe concentrations of four dissolved nutrients (NO_3 , NH_4 , PO_4 , SiO_2), two functional groups of phytoplankton (diatoms, flagellates), micro- and meso-zooplankton, detritus (nitrogen and phosphorus), detritus-silicon, and oxygen (Figure 1). Pelagic detrital silicon was added to better describe the cycling and settling of silicon in deep waters. The model currency is nitrogen using Redfield ratios to convert to phosphorus and silicon. Chlorophyll *a* (Chl *a*) was estimated as the sum of the two phytoplankton groups multiplied by a factor of 1.7 mg-Chl/mmol-N. The calanoid copepod *Calanus finmarchicus* generally dominates the mesozooplankton biomass and the physiological processes were parameterized according to previous studies. The model considers the processes of nutrient uptake, growth, grazing, egestion, respiration, recycling, mortality, particle sinking, and seasonal mesozooplankton migration in the water column and overwintering in bottom waters. Net primary production was estimated as daily means of phytoplankton growth after subtracting respiration and integrated over 30 m depth corresponding to the productive layer. The timing of the seasonal *C. finmarchicus* migration was calibrated against *in situ* measurements of their vertical distribution over time. Light optimum was changed for both phytoplankton groups during calibration to fit with the timing of the spring bloom. Background mortality of microzooplankton was increased to account for other grazing pressure than from *C. finmarchicus*.

3.2. Spatio-temporal patterns of zooplankton biomass and production

In ARCHFISH, the FlexSem hydrodynamic model has been improved by implementing a new 2nd order advection-diffusion scheme. The scheme uses both the up- and down-wind concentrations and a limiter to ensure numerical stability. This new scheme is a considerable improvement in this area, as it has much less numerical diffusion and therefore maintains gradients more accurately. Furthermore, the surface wind drag parameterization has been updated to a parabolic formulation, which yields higher and more realistic wind drag and generation of surface turbulence at intermediate wind speeds.

Figure 2: a) Depth of the model domain. The dotted and solid lines mark the 150- and 350-meter contour lines, respectively. b) Resolution of the model mesh (from 1.8 km to 16 km).

Overall, the simulations with lower- and higher-order advection schemes produce the same horizontal distribution of surface chlorophyll, with the highest concentrations within Disko Bay and Hellefisk Bank, just south of the Bay (Figure 3). However, the implementation of a higher-order advection scheme has improved the representation of fronts in the model, leading to stronger horizontal gradients in chlorophyll concentrations and larger horizontal variability.

Figure 3: Modeled surface chlorophyll concentration on the 23rd of May 2004 from a) previous hydrodynamical model setup, and b) current model setup with new advection scheme. The white line marks an ice concentration of 10%.

The mean surface concentration of zooplankton in the model domain shows that the highest concentrations are found in within Disko Bay, especially in the northern area where the melting water from Sermeq Kujalleq, the most active glacier on the Greenland Ice Sheet, flows out of the bay, driving nutrient upwelling and sustaining phytoplankton growth, which in turn leads to high concentrations of zooplankton.

Looking at the interannual variability, the years 2010 and 2011 stand out as years with the highest zooplankton concentration (Figure 4). These years are likewise the years with the longest period of ice-free days (Figure 5), showing how light limitation has an impact on productivity in the bay. However, the

years following 2011 do not show a correlation between ice-free days and zooplankton concentration, indication that nutrient limitation plays a larger role at this time, likely due to a time lag in the resupply following the depletion in the years 2010 and 2011. This suggests that changes in the physical conditions has an impact higher in the food chain, which is longer lived than the physical phenomenons themselves.

Figure 4: Average) Mean surface concentration of zooplankton in Disko Bay from 2004 to 2017. Years) Bias from the long-term mean in surface zooplankton concentration for each year.

Figure 5: Mean ice-free period (days) from 2004 to 2018.

3.3. Shrimp biophysical model

In Disko Bay, Greenland, shrimp (*Pandalus borealis*) represent a key species both ecologically and economically. The contribution of the fishery industry to Greenland's GDP makes up approximately 25% (2016 to 2021, European Commission, 2023), but in 2025, the Total Allowable Catch (TAC) of shrimp was reduced to 83.000 T/yr, down from recent year's TAC of above 100.000 T/yr. This reduction was based on knowledge of reduced shrimp stock and catch rates from the Greenland Institute of Natural Resources (https://natur.gl/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Raadgivning_rejer_2025_DK.pdf). Understanding the early life stages of shrimp is critical for predicting population dynamics and responses to environmental change. However, the complex interplay between physical oceanographic conditions and larval development remains insufficiently understood. In ARCFISH, a novel biophysical model is being developed, integrating ocean circulation patterns and temperature variability, to simulate the dispersal and survival of shrimp larvae in Disko Bay. By coupling biological processes with high-resolution physical data, the model aims to improve predictions of larval transport pathways and settlement success and thus making it possible to develop indices to support sustainable fisheries in a rapidly changing Arctic.

Figure 6: a) Start position of particles, blue colour marks particles released in Disko Bay. b) Density plot of 90-day tracks for all start positions c) Density plot of 90-day tracks for Disko Bay start-positions (blue marks in subplot a).

P. borealis have a relatively long pelagic larvae stage of 2 to 3 months (Le Corre et al., 2019). At stage 1 of the larvae development, they are located in the surface water but descend deeper into the water column through stages 2 to 5. As a first approach to modelling shrimp larvae dispersal, we released particles in the surface water of the model domain, in a grid of 1x1 km (Figure 6a), and let them drift freely, assuming a pelagic larvae duration (PLD) of 85 days. From this simulation, we were able to assess locations of retention, with larvae released in Disko Bay, largely staying within the bay during the simulation period (Figure 6c), suggesting a large degree of retention, especially in bathymetry-controlled eddies. In the shelf area outside of the bay, the largescale currents impact the tracks to a larger degree, and retention areas are not seen to the same degree (Figure 6b).

The next step entails simulations of larvae drift, in which the release time is guided by temperature. This makes it possible to assess interannual variation in larvae release and how it affects the drift. The locations in which the larvae can settle will be limited to areas determined as appropriate shrimp habitat (Figure 7) following Krawczyk et al., (2023). The updated model of shrimp larvae transport will be run for the years 2004 to 2018 and will thus enable the assessment of how larvae drift and settlement are affected by differing physical conditions in different years, e.g. temperature, melting and large-scale circulation patterns.

Figure 7: Shrimp habitat model (Krawczyk et al., 2023. Figure 5a).

3.4. Ecological indices for fisheries

Development of model products to make indicators of fish resources has been limited. So far, to our knowledge, no ecosystem models have been incorporated in assessments for use in ecosystem management systems for any Arctic region. Hence, it is important to continue developing more

comprehensive models and relevant indicators to inform managers on food web interactions and changes, and stock distributions and biomass.

The updated spatio-temporal patterns of zooplankton biomass and productivity will be compared with environmental monitoring data and fish stocks to make new indices for fishery in collaboration with stakeholders in the next version.

4. Time-series of environmental data

4.1. Time-series data collection

While significant progress has been made in collecting observational data on ocean biogeochemistry thanks to the development of satellite sensors, autonomous platforms like Argo and gliders, and ship-based campaigns like GO-SHIP, data scarcity and heterogeneity remain challenging, especially at high latitudes. Thus, integration of these datasets with advanced modelling for more comprehensive monitoring and forecasting of the ocean's complex systems is necessary. For this purpose, selected outputs of reanalysis models and forecasts are produced to provide extensive information on the environmental background for fishery data. Time series for spatial fields of selected relevant variables (nutrients, carbon cycle, ocean acidity, oxygen, chlorophyll, phytoplankton and zooplankton concentrations) in addition to physical variables (temperature, salinity, and ocean currents) are obtained from the available CMEMS products, like:

- Global Ocean Physics Reanalysis GLORYS12V1 (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00021>)
- Global Ocean Real time in-situ observations objective analysis (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00037>),
- Global Ocean Delayed Mode gridded CORA In-situ Observations objective analysis in Delayed Mode (<https://doi.org/10.17882/46219>),
- Global Ocean In-Situ Near-Real-Time Observations (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00036>),
- Global Ocean Biogeochemistry Analysis and Forecast (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00015>),
- Arctic Ocean Biogeochemistry Analysis and Forecast (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00003>),
- Nutrient and carbon profiles vertical distribution (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00048>).

The GLOBAL_ANALYSISFORECAST_BGC_001_028 is produced at Mercator Ocean International (Toulouse, France). It provides 10 days of 3D global ocean forecasts updated weekly. It provides biogeochemical fields of chlorophyll concentration, nitrate, phosphate, silicate, dissolved oxygen, dissolved iron, primary production, phytoplankton, pH, dissolved inorganic carbon, total alkalinity, surface partial pressure of carbon dioxide, light attenuation coefficient and zooplankton.

The global ocean output files are displayed with a 1/4-degree horizontal resolution with a regular longitude/latitude equirectangular projection. 50 vertical levels range from 0 to 5500 meters.

This product is based on the PISCES biogeochemical model. It is forced offline at a daily frequency by GLOBAL_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_001_024 coarsened at 1/4 degree, with SEEK-based Data Assimilation

of OCEANCOLOUR_GLO_BGC_L4_NRT_009_102. The PISCES biogeochemical model is available on the NEMO (<https://www.nemo-ocean.eu/>) modelling platform.

To illustrate the recent changes in the upper, productive layers of the ocean, four chosen locations of similar water depth (two west of Greenland and two north-west of Iceland, Figure 8), representing various domains of the North Atlantic, as shown in the example spatial distribution at 25 m in May 2025 of four variables retrieved from biogeochemical models (Figure 9). Further, time series of nitrate, phosphate, silicate, chlorophyll, phytoplankton (Dec 2021 – Aug 2025), and zooplankton concentrations (Dec 2023 – Aug 2025) from ocean surface to bottom are plotted (Figures 10-15).

Figure 8: Four locations chosen to display time series from BIOMER4V2R1 and BIO4GLO12 models with monthly data spanning from December 2021 to August 2025, and from December 2023 to August 2025, respectively.

Figure 9: Maps of the outputs from BIOMER4V2R1 and BIO4GLO12 models: a) phosphorus, b) chlorophyll, phytoplankton and d) zooplankton concentrations on 1st May 2025 at depth of 25 m.

An important question is the prediction of nutrient limitation. For this, the Redfield ratio (C: N: P \approx 106: 16: 1 in the ocean) is used to determine whether nitrogen or phosphorus is the limiting nutrient for phytoplankton growth. Monitoring changes in ocean chemistry by analyzing deviations from the Redfield ratio can indicate shifts in ocean conditions, such as changes in nutrient availability or the influence of human activities. The new collection of biogeochemical time series and outputs of biogeochemical reanalysis and forecasts allows the development of new products for sustainable fisheries in the subpolar and polar regions.

Figure 10: Time series of nitrate from four locations: a) Disko Bay, b) West Greenland, c) west of Iceland and d) north of Iceland, from BIOMER4V2R1 model with monthly data spanning from December 2021 to August 2025.

Figure 11: Time series of phosphate from four locations: a) Disko Bay, b) West Greenland, c) west of Iceland and d) north of Iceland, from BIOMER4V2R1 model with monthly data spanning from December 2021 to August 2025.

Figure 12: Time series of silicate from four locations: a) Disko Bay, b) West Greenland, c) west of Iceland and d) north of Iceland, from BIOMER4V2R1 model with monthly data spanning from December 2021 to August 2025.

Figure 13: Time series of chlorophyll concentration from four locations: a) Disko Bay, b) West Greenland, c) west of Iceland and d) north of Iceland, from BIOMER4V2R1 model with monthly data spanning from December 2021 to August 2025.

Figure 14: Time series of phytoplankton concentration from four locations: a) Disko Bay, b) West Greenland, c) west of Iceland and d) north of Iceland, from BIOMER4V2R1 model with monthly data spanning from December 2021 to August 2025.

Figure 15: Time series of zooplankton concentration from four locations: a) Disko Bay, b) West Greenland, c) west of Iceland and d) north of Iceland, from BIO4GLO12 model with monthly data spanning from December 2023 to August 2025.

Currently, the Argo Program (Argo, 2025) is an important source of observational data on ocean biogeochemistry. Nevertheless, the data coverage is sparse in the shallow seas and where the sea ice is

present. For the West Greenland and Iceland shelves, it is particularly challenging. All available BGC Argo floats in these regions, or nearby, are plotted in Figure 16, showing large, unsurveyed areas closer to the coastline.

An example of valuable float data is shown in Figure 17, where the development of the deep mixed layer (ML) during winter 2024/2025 is depicted with its maximum reaching 600 m in the end of March 2025, with the highest concentration of oxygen concentration at the base of the newly formed ML, and its further restratification and depletion of the oxygen concentration during the following spring/summer.

Figure 16: Trajectories of all BGC Argo floats active in 2025 in the regions (or nearby) of a) West Greenland and b) Iceland shelves.

Figure 17: Data retrieved from the selected BGC Argo float active in 2025 south of Iceland: a) trajectory of the instrument, b) adjusted temperature, and c) adjusted oxygen concentration along the float's pathway.

These data were collected and made freely available by the International Argo Program and the national programs that contribute to it (<https://argo.ucsd.edu>, <https://www.ocean-ops.org>). The Argo Program is part of the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS).

4.2. Spatio-temporal patterns of key variables for fisheries

During the next phase of the project, spatio-temporal patterns of key environmental variables relevant for biology and fisheries will be obtained based on available objectively mapped in situ observations and reanalysis products, including CMEMS products listed in Section 4.1 and other available sources. Tools will be developed for visualisation of spatio-temporal changes along selected sections (as Hovmöller diagrams) or spatial anomalies of selected properties from their long-term means. Sea surface properties (SST, SSS, SSC) will be obtained from satellite products and used to identify spatial patterns in the surface layer and their anomalies from the long-term means. Tools to calculate spatial distributions of derived quantities, including mean temperature, salinity and density in the upper layer, mixed layer depth, water column stability, thermocline and pycnocline depth, heat content in the upper layer, and other will be developed as Python scripts, ready for containerization and use in Blue Insight DTO platform.

5. Fishery-dependent data products

Fisheries-dependent data (FDD) products are information outputs derived from data collected directly from fishing activities, by systems supporting or monitoring fishing activities. These data streams are often generated while fishing is taking place and are essential for fisheries management and stock assessment, monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS), supporting ecosystem-based management and food traceability and estimation of carbon footprint of fishing activities.

Generating FDD is often a challenging task, especially in small-scale fisheries (SSF) and recreational fisheries (RF). An overarching issue with SSF and RF are that these types of fisheries are in general data-poor, which is preventing their MCS and fisheries management. SSF represents at least 40% of the global fisheries catches (Duke University and WorldFish, 2022) and the stocks they target are often unassessed and are generally in substantially worse condition than assessed fisheries (Costello, et al., 2012). RF are becoming a major component of the exploitation of coastal and marine resources within EU member states, but MCS and reliable data on such catches are lacking (Brownscombe, et al. 2019).

This chapter will give a short summary of main data sources for FDD and how these data streams can be utilized for better forecasting, monitoring and planning that could contribute to the pilot ARCFISH DTO, delivering new data products and services in support of sustainable Arctic Fisheries.

5.1. Fisheries-dependent data (FDD), collection and data utilization.

Vessel Monitoring System (VMS) is an onboard electronic satellite-based tracking system that automatically transmits a vessel's position, speed, and heading at regular intervals, usually every 30 minutes to 2 hours, via satellite or cellular networks to surveillance centres. It is mandatory for most commercial fishing vessels above a certain size in most fishing areas, depending on the country or Regional Fisheries Management Organization (RFMO). All vessels above 12m in length in EU waters must carry a VMS system, which is one of the most important tools for sustainable fisheries management and for fighting illegal, unreported, and unregulated (IUU) fishing.

The VMS uses GPS coordinates to determine position and sends encrypted data via satellite to relevant authorities. These position reports are automatically sent at set intervals, usually every half an hour. These reports include fishing vessel ID, latitude & longitude, speed and direction and also include a timestamp.

The monitoring authorities view vessels' positions on digital maps (GIS), which is important for rescue or emergency response and to see if the vessel enters a restricted area.

In Europe, electronic recording and reporting systems (ERS) are used to record, report, process, store and send fisheries data. The key element is the electronic logbook where usually the captain of a fishing vessel keeps the records of the fishing operations. The records are then sent to the national authorities, which store the information in a secure database and utilize the data for monitoring, control and surveillance and to ensure regulatory compliance by the vessel. These e-logbooks are basically an electronic edition of the paper-based logbooks that have been used for decades. The captain of the vessel usually enters information regarding the catch, by haul or days, depending on the type of fisheries. Catch reports are created with information on the catch volumes by species, catch location, date, weather conditions and other factors. The information from the logbooks is often checked when the fish is landed by weighing the catches and comparing with the information supplied in the logbooks.

Newer versions of ERS integrate automated data collection directly from vessel sensors and monitoring equipment. This reduces manual input and increases data accuracy. For example, in addition to the manually entered catch details (species, kg, avg. weight), the system can automatically capture environmental parameters such as windspeed, sea surface and bottom temperature, and gear information.

Automatic data collection also extends into production processes on board. Modern processing lines can be connected to ERS databases so that information such as product weights, grading, glazing, packaging units, freezer loads, and tank capacity is registered directly from production machinery. For instance, the attributes shown in the schema (Figure 18) — actual weight, packaging no of units, freezer start_time/stop_time — can be logged automatically, creating a direct link between catch reporting and production output.

By combining manual reporting with automated inputs from both vessel operations and production systems, modern ERS platforms provide richer, more reliable datasets for fisheries science, compliance, and value-chain traceability, while also reducing the reporting burden on vessel crews.

Trip information
vessel_name
callsign
registration
trip_id
trip_is_closed
nr_within_year
crew_count
captain_name
captain_id
departure_time
departure_port_name
departure_port_id
departure_locode
departure_country
arrival_time
landing_time
landing_port_name
landing_port_id
landing_locode
landing_country

Haul information
haul_nr
haul_is_closed
fishing_permit
comments
special_remark
region
relevant_area
fishing_zone
target_species
fishing_operation_start
haul_start_time
haul_start_position_lat
haul_start_position_lon
haul_start_bottom_depth
haul_start_headline_depth
haul_start_headline_temp
haul_end_time
haul_end_position_lat
haul_end_position_lon
haul_end_bottom_depth

Environmental parameters
wind_speed
wind_direction
sea_condition
bottom_type
air_temperature
sea_surface_temperature
bottom_temperature_min
bottom_temperature_max

Gear info
gear_category_id
gear_local_id
gear_local_name
gear_category_name
gear_code

Catch
species_id
species_name
total_kg
avg_weight

Product
product_id
product_name
short_name
product_code
ext_code
description1
description2
description3
round_weight
actual_weight
current_kg_price
currency
current_price
lot
glazed
undersized
material_id
material_name
avg_weight
grade

Packaging
unit_weight
nr_of_units
nominal_weight

Freezer
freezer_name
freezer_lot
units
start_time
stop_time

Tanks
Tank name
capacity
quantity
ver_position
hor_position

Figure 18: Example of information that are or can be reported in an TrackWell logbook system.

Today, suppliers of seafood into the EU must also provide a catch certificate with each lot, to prove that their supply is not coming from illegal, unreported or unregulated (IUU) fisheries. The demand for these certificates will most probably further enhance the use of electronic logbooks in the North Atlantic (Thakur and Gunnlaugsson, 2018) and probably also in the Arctic. The electronic logbooks create large amounts of data concerning the catch. It is therefore important for all stakeholders in the value chain to ascertain

how they can get value from the data gathered in the electronic logbook (Figure 18). Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems in fishing and processing companies manage data from processing, inventory control, lot tracking, logistics and sometimes marketing. These systems are used to record usage of raw material/work in progress and all associated costs and maintain full product records including price, sales, and production history. These systems are usually the backbone of each company and can usually import information from vessel logbooks (Thakur and Gunnlaugsson, 2018).

Electronic Monitoring (EM) refers to the use of onboard cameras, sensors, and GPS to record and verify fishing activity, providing digital records of what takes place on the fishing vessel during fishing. These EM systems usually record at various frame rates and resolutions tailored to specific operational requirements. Event-based or continuous streaming via Starlink can enable real-time AI processing. This capability allows immediate risk assessment and decision making, optimizing video review processes and enhancing overall efficiency. Starlink provides cost effective high-speed broadband internet, ensuring uninterrupted data transfer from vessels to “the cloud”, supporting real-time compliance. These systems are getting more common in the EU fleet, especially in demersal and pelagic fisheries. There are possibilities to integrate EM event-based data with VMS, e-logbooks and other data streams to enhance monitoring, data quality and compliance, the DTO could be a part of that integration. That could strengthen the capacity of Blue Economy actors such as fisheries scientists, fisheries managers and decision-makers at European, national, regional and local level to design and utilize integrated tools and processes, to make fisheries more sustainable, enhancing transparency and trust in the seafood supply chains and restoring ocean health.

In this project, VMS data has been integrated with fishing data (e.g. catch information from logbooks) and other relevant data (e.g. ecosystem and resource management data) which can have huge potential for stakeholders (e.g. fishing companies, research communities, resource managers, and MCS sectors). Figure 19 illustrates integration of vessel movement and trawl data into the Blue Insight DTO platform.

Figure 19: Vessel movement and trawl data from Brim pelagic fisheries, displayed in the Blue Insight DTO platform.

Next steps in the project will be to further combine Fisheries-dependent data, with Fisheries-independent data and integrate that into the DTO. Fishery-independent information can include oceanographic-, meteorological, social, and economic data. This could support new model projections and powerful analysis tools in a DTO platform, that could open for novel ways of investigating and visualising trends and patterns in species distribution and abundance, supporting sustainable fisheries and resource management in a growing Blue Economy.

6. Creation of a Regional Database for sustainable fisheries in the Arctic

Kongsberg Discovery will develop a regional database (Figure 20) to support data integration and accessibility across the designated use-case areas of Greenland and Iceland. This database will serve as a centralized platform for aggregating diverse environmental, fisheries, and oceanographic datasets collected by project partners and stakeholders. The system will be designed to efficiently store, organize, and manage both time-series and spatial data, including measurements from sensors, remote sensing, and fishery-dependent sources.

Emphasizing interoperability and scalability, the regional database will incorporate standardized metadata and data formatting protocols to ensure seamless data sharing and retrieval. The database will be implemented with Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standards in mind, to ease integration with other DTO initiatives. The database will provide data, and links to external sources of data hosted in other regional and global databases.

The database will be integrated with the Blue Insight DTO platform for the project partners and provide access aggregated model and in-situ data, and the capability of loading complete datasets from other sources.

Figure 20: The regional database, as it will be integrated into the Blue Insight DTO platform.

The regional database will consist of spatio-temporal data in OGC-compliant data formats with connected assets. Assets will primarily be hosted at the project partners data centers (NMDC, eCUDO, etc.) or in European or global repositories like GEBCO (General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans), EMODNET (European Marine Observation and Data Network), or Copernicus. The asset catalog contains more complex data elements like videos, pictures, model data, gridded data and timeseries data (CTDs, XBTs, etc.).

7. Summary and next steps

Model output of copepods and shrimps will be imported into the ARCFISH DTO to be analyzed against other observations, such as temperature, salinity, and presence of predatory species to better understand migration patterns. This will induce new indicators of fish resources that will increase knowledge of the spatial and seasonal distributions of fish and shrimp stocks for the fishery sector and managers to better support a sustainable fishery in the Blue Economy.

In this project, fisheries-dependent data like VMS data and fishing data (e.g. catch information from logbooks) has been combined with other relevant data (e.g. ecosystem and resource management data) that can have huge potential value for Blue Economy stakeholders like fishing companies, research communities, resource managers, and MCS sectors. Next steps in the project will be to combine fisheries-

dependent data, further with fisheries-independent data and integrate that into the ARCFISH DTO. This could support new model projections and powerful analysis tools in a DTO platform, that could open for novel ways of investigating and visualising trends and patterns in species distribution and abundance, supporting sustainable fisheries and resource management, and providing valuable tools to bolster the Blue Economy.

A developed toolbox/GUI dedicated to a better understanding of the spatio-temporal patterns of key environmental variables will be developed, allowing for calculation and further plotting of maps in the Blue Insight DTO platform. Here is an example set of key variables:

- Mixed layer depth – the stratification of the upper layer of the ocean
- Upper ocean (50 m) temperature and salinity
- Subsurface ocean (50-100 m) temperature and salinity
- Ocean chemistry and nutrient distribution
- Depth of thermocline, halocline and pycnocline
- Depth of chlorophyll maximum
- Upper ocean (100 m) zooplankton concentration

Kongsberg Discovery will proceed with developing the Blue Insight solutions, focusing on visualizations, automatic data processing solutions, integrations, and progress to work on the regional database. By integrating ecological models, environmental time-series, and fisheries-dependent data, Blue Insight will support informed decision-making for sustainable Arctic fisheries.

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